

ELECTRON IRRADIATION INDUCED CRYSTALLINE AMOPHIZATION AT SiO₂ SURFACE LAYER OF SiC PARTICLES IN A SiC_p/AL COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The structures of surface SiO₂ layer of oxidized silicon carbide before and after compositing with aluminum matrix were studied by XRD and TEM. It is shown that the surface SiO₂ layer is crystalline when silicon carbide particles are oxidized at the temperature of 1100°C in the air. It will be amorphized under the irradiation of high energy electron beam after being compositing with aluminum matrix. It was found by EDX analysis that there existed a concentration gradient of aluminum across the SiO₂ layer. The amorphization mechanism of the SiO₂ layer was also discussed on the basis of qualitative thermodynamics and kinetic considerations.

KEYWORDS: amorphization, electron irradiation, induced, SiC particle, oxidization, SiO₂, surface layer, crystalline, aluminum matrix

INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognized that introducing an oxide layer (SiO₂) on the surface of SiC plays an important role in preventing SiC from being attacked by liquid Al, improving its wettability and also improving the fracture strain of the SiC_p/Al composites [1,2,3]. Nevertheless, as for the structure of surface oxidized layer of SiC particles, there exist different views. Some investigators believe that the oxidation of SiC below 1200°C produces amorphous silica [4,5], but according to other researchers' result [6], heat treatment of the SiC particulates in the temperature range of 800-1100°C produces a crystalline SiO₂ layer of tetragonal and hexagonal structures.

The purpose of this communication is to report a new observation concerned with *in situ* electron irradiation studies using transmission electron microscopy (TEM). In this particular case a crystalline to amorphous transformation is observed. Although the electron irradiation induced crystalline amorphization is well known in ionization-sensitive materials, so far it has not been observed to occur in such composite systems.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

SiC particles used in this work is green α - SiC abrasives with an average diameter of 60 μm . The particles used were in an artificially oxidized condition. Oxidation was carried out in air at 1100⁰C for 10 hours using a Al₂O₃ crucible heated in an electric furnace. The phases formed after oxidization were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using nickel-filtered Cu K α radiation.

The composite samples were manufactured by squeeze casting technology in the matrix of commercial pure aluminum. Transmission electron microscopes (PHILIPS CM 12, JEM-200CX) were used. The interface microstructure was examined by using bright field(BF) images, dark field(DF) images, selected area diffraction(SAD), electron energy loss spectroscopy(EELS) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy(EDX). The TEM thin foils were prepared by ion milling at 12 degree with a voltage of 4 kv after mechanical polishing and dimpling.

RESULTS

The XRD result (Fig.1) shows that the oxidized SiC particles consist of two different phases identified as hexagonal α - SiC and pseudohexagonal SiO₂. Intensities of α - SiC peaks are much higher than those of the SiO₂. According to the oxidation process, it is reasonable to deduct that the oxidized SiC is composed of a SiC core and a SiO₂ surface shell. At this time, the SiO₂ phase is crystalline.

Fig.1 X-ray diffraction pattern of oxidized SiC

A layer of about 500 nm was observed on the surface of oxidized SiC at the Al/SiC interface (Fig.2a), and its diffraction pattern and corresponding dark field image were shown in Figs.2b, 2c. It is interesting to find that the layer becomes unstable under the radiation of high energy electron beam. Only after about two minutes the SAD pattern of the SiO₂ layer became a halo ring (Fig.3a) which is characteristic of an amorphous phase. Diffraction spots outside the halo ring are from aluminum matrix. It is a pity that a symmetric low index pattern of crystalline SiO₂ could not be obtained due to the rapid transformation from crystalline to

amorphous. Nevertheless, according to the indexing of the obtained diffraction pattern(Fig.2b), there exists some diffraction spots which corresponds strong X-ray diffraction peaks (such as $d=0.407$ nm) of the crystalline SiO_2 . Fig.3b is the morphology of the SiO_2 oxidation layer after irradiation of the electron beam for about two minutes. Compared with its morphology before the transformation (Fig.2a), the two contrasts under TEM are different. The SiO_2 layer before the transformation showed typical contrast variation with the tilt of the specimen. This indicates that the SiO_2 layer before irradiation are crystalline in nature. On the other hand, the SiO_2 layer after the transformation showed no distinct diffraction contrast at any orientation and its diffraction patterns typically consisted of only halo rings as shown in Fig.3a. The absence of any diffraction contrast indicates the presence of an amorphous phase.

Fig.2 Morphology of SiO_2 layer at SiC/Al interface before the transformation
 (a)bright field image (b)diffraction pattern (c)dark field image

Fig.3 Morphology of SiO_2 layer at SiC/Al interface after the transformation
 (a)halo ring diffraction (b)bright field image

EELS analysis performed on the oxidized SiC shows a strong presence of O and Si peaks. Fig.4 shows the obtained electron energy loss spectrums of the amorphous layer. Comparing with Fig.5, we can see that the amorphous layer contains silicon element whose valence state is plus four and oxygen element whose valence state is negative two. So, we confirm the amorphous layer is amorphous SiO_2 layer. The EDX chemical analysis of the amorphous layer (Fig.6) was performed using a 100 nm diameter electron beam. We find that there exists a concentration gradient of aluminum. Obviously this is caused by the diffusion of aluminum.

Fig.4 Electron energy loss spectrums of amorphous layer
(a) Silicon edge (b) Oxygen edge

Fig.5 Standard electron energy loss spectrums
(a) Silicon $L_{2,3}$ edge of SiO_2 (b) Oxygen K edge of Al_2O_3

Fig.6 Concentration gradient of aluminum in the SiO_2 layer

From the above experimental results, it can be concluded that when SiC particles are heated at temperature of 1100°C, crystalline SiO₂ layer firstly forms. After the oxidized SiC particles were composited with commercial pure aluminum, the crystalline SiO₂ layer transforms to amorphous SiO₂ layer under the irradiation of high energy(200kv) electron beam. Due to the rapid transformation process, only by careful observation can the phenomenon be observed. Thus, the difference between X-ray diffraction result and electron diffraction result is explained. It helps to understand the combining mechanism of SiC and Al matrix.

DISCUSSION

The present results are interesting in the radiation damage field since the crystalline silica layer has been made amorphous with such mild damage conditions. A proper combination of thermodynamic and kinetic factors is necessary for amorphization to occur. The basic requirements for a crystal to glass transformation are [7]: (I) a large negative heat of mixing of the constituent elements and (II) a large disparity in the diffusivities of the elements involved in the transformation. Criteria (I) makes the glassy phase thermodynamically stable with respect to the crystalline reactants while criteria (II) kinetically favours growth of the amorphous phase as opposed to the crystalline products.

The strong Al-O, Si-O, Al-C and Si-C bond strengths suggest that these elements have large negative heats of mixing as binary systems. Therefore, it is proposed that in the Al/SiO₂/SiC system examined, the strong attraction between Al, C, Si and O results in an amorphous mixture of these elements that has a lower free energy than the Al and SiC crystals with a thin layer of silica in between. It is possible that O, which has a strong affinity for Al, Si and C, binds and stabilizes the amorphous phase. Formation of competing crystalline phases such as Al₄C₃ and Al₂O₃ which probably have higher thermodynamic stability than the Al-Si-C-O phase has to be kinetically suppressed in order for the amorphous phase to form.

Based on the results of this study, the following mechanism is proposed to explain the amorphization at the Al/SiO₂/SiC interface. At the manufacturing temperature of the SiC_p/Al composite, nascent Al comes into contact with the silica on the surface of SiC. As Al has a high affinity for C and O, while SiC is relatively stable, hence Al diffuses into the silica. Because manufacturing process is short and manufacturing temperature is not high enough, the diffusion process may not be fully carried out. When an energetic electron strikes an atom in the SiO₂ crystal, a substantial energy transfer occurs and the atom is displaced and set in motion. It in turn collides with other atoms setting up a displacement cascade during which many atoms are relocated in the lattice. The displacement process can be viewed as an isotropic random walk [8]. It was shown that radiation induced atomic mixing of a diffusion couple can be thought of as a very high temperature diffusion process(10⁴ K or so) which takes place in very short time intervals (10⁻¹¹-10⁻¹² second). The overall composition profile evolution is the result of many uncorrelated displacement spikes. So, the diffusion of aluminum is sped up. The presence of Al in the amorphous layer with the lack of Si or C diffusion into Al indicates that there is a large disparity in the diffusivities of the elements involved in the transformation.

Of course, when discussing amorphization process, the effects of the defects produced by the collision cascade can not be neglected. These defects include interstitial atom-vacancy pairs as well as other types of defects such as vacancy loops and possible chemical disordering by

irradiation, etc. The presence of such defects should destabilize crystalline solid solutions with respect to glass formation. All the above factors support the amorphization and hence the amorphous phase forms.

Much work remains to be done to find out the conditions (composition, temperature, dose rate, electron energy, etc) under which amorphization occurs. Fundamental insight into the atomic mechanisms of the amorphization is lacking in this preliminary work and will require extensive further experimentation.

CONCLUSIONS

XRD and TEM studies show that the surface SiO₂ layer is crystalline when SiC particles are oxidized at the temperature of 1100°C in the air, but it will be amorphized under the irradiation of high energy electron beam after composited with commercial pure aluminum matrix. The crystal to glass transformation is explained on the basis of qualitative thermodynamics and kinetic considerations.

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